

ISic2942

I.Sicily inscription 2942

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2003

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332185

1. [Τιττ]έλου άγ [ορανόμου] ²⁷Άγη[σίππου] (vel sim., Lazzarini)²⁷.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644851

EDCS 70900016

PHI 332185

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0829

Nenci, G. 1991. Florilegio epigrafico segestano. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. 21: 920-929. At 927 no.4 tav.300.2

De Vido, S. 1991. appendice: fonti letterarie, epigrafiche, numismatiche, etc.. *ASNP*. 21: 929-994. At 974

De Vido, S. 2003. Genealogie Segestane. *Quarte Giornate Internazionali di Studi sull'area elima, Erice, 1-4 dicembre 2000*. Pisa. pp. 367-402. At 399 no.10

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta*. Pisa. At G26

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2942. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387771>